

Impacts of Women Librarian's Participation in Community Development Projects in Zaria Metropolis of Kaduna State, Nigeria

Boor, M. C. H.¹

Email: leemboor15@gmail.com

Tel: 08028198034

Takai, G.²

Email: takaigrace@gmail.com

Tel: 08054184809

Suleiman, H.³

Email: hijarasuleiman@gmail.com

Tel: 09020999246

¹Department of Educational Foundation and Curriculum, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

²Kashim Ibrahim Library, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

³Library Unit, Division of Agricultural Colleges, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Abstract

This study investigated the impact of women's librarian participation in community development projects in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Two research questions were posed to guide the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 260 women Librarians in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State. The sample of the study was 176 women librarians selected through a purposive sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers. The instrument for data collection was validated by three experts. The consistency of the instrument was ensured using Cronbach Alpha with a reliability co-efficient of 0.86. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. A mean score of 2.53 was used as a decision rule. The findings revealed the factors that hinder women librarians' participation in community development projects, range from poor financial status, cultural limitations on women, and gender base in project selection. The findings also revealed strategies for effective implementation of women librarians' participation in community development projects, which ranges from encouraging women librarians' participation in development activities to ensuring authentic participation and maintaining cordial relationships with women. It was recommended that women should be given equal rights and opportunities to participate in the decision-making process

Keywords: Women Librarian, Gender, Community development projects.

Introduction

Before the 21st century, Nigeria women were restricted by custom, standards and religion in the society. The elevated degree of ignorance among women further deteriorates the mishap. Also, women were thought of as the main really great for child-bearing and support, food readiness and taking care of the entire relations, to centered on cultivating and unimportant business, (Kay & Higuera, 2019). Further stated, women most significant stores come from the current enlightening mores which consign the women to the kitchen and distribute them the place of housewife or mother. Routinely, the portrayal of women has been that of a wife/spouse or mother while their obligation was to really focus on the man and nothing too. In International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) (2019) reported that, out of a rough 2.4 billion oppressed individuals on the planet more than 66% are women. Further explanation made sense that women hopeless destitution in demands for sufficient food, water and medical services. Also, women need" admittance to the basic assets of credit, land, and inheritance. Considering the above mentioned clearly, women are denied decisions and potential open doors and decision-making both at home and locally is immaterial. In most piece of Nigeria, similar to North-West Nigeria, women are not approved to take part or participate in some community/local development projects/undertakings or exercises in the society. Enemu, (2011) found that the standard of women is collectively and politically avoided from partaking in community

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development projects, arranging/decision-marking, and dynamic cycles. Research by Imhabekhai, (2019) posits that women who address an impressive extent of the all-out populace in Nigeria are illiterates. In support, Gbenga and James, (2019) affirmed that women procure not as much since they are in fields that are less fundamental and less compensated which additionally denies them from taking part in community development projects. It further explained that the absence of dynamic power influences women politically in society.

Without a doubt, Ike, (2015) reported that women need to get consent from their husbands/spouses to go to an exercise or work outside the home. They were not given the option to cast a ballot in a few delicate situations, community denied them the open doors, for example, they needed the dynamic ability to take interest on an equivalent premise with men. One of the presumptions behind the development is that everybody has something to add to the existence of the community. From this guess, it becomes relevant that women who comprise an enormous extent of Nigeria's populace could add to the existence of their community (Asogwa, 2019). Also, difficulties militating against the participation of women in community development projects for example absence of the executives' expertise, clashes, literacy/obliviousness, misappropriation of societal assets, unfortunate carry out of open assets, pay off and debasement among the partners, absence of preparation systems, absence of co-activity among partners and community pioneers, absence of managerial abilities, unfortunate responsibility, unfortunate initiative abilities, deficient exposure, orientation segregation, absence of women association, and self - centered interest of certain pioneers (Ewelum & Madu 2016). It depends on these difficulties that the review plan to give an outline about a few calculated systems like community development that could assist with tending to the above challenges by women librarians. Women librarians emerged as the Association for the Welfare of Women Librarians in Nigeria (AWWLIN) order wise referred to as AWLIN in 2013. This was for the purpose of consolidating the unity of the entire Women Librarians, archivists, and Information Scientists in Nigeria as a body of practitioners in the profession. Also, promoting their welfare in order to contribute positively and effectively to the utilization of the educational, cultural, and information resources of Nigeria and to enhance the dignity of women in Nigeria. This came with the birth of the Kaduna State AWLIN in 2019. However, the fact that the Association of Women Librarians in Nigeria (AWLIN) Kaduna State Chapter had to form, organize, and hold conferences, seminars and workshops on community development projects and gender empowerment, AWLIN had suggested and agreed that Nigeria women are not adequately empowered in their societies and aware of the needs for women to participate in community development projects in order to empower the girl child and women. So that they could be strong and resourceful, able to give their maximum contribution to develop Kaduna state and Nigeria as a whole. The participation of women librarians in community development projects is a means to achieve the goals of development, by uniting all women interested in Librarianship, Archivist and Information Scientists establish and develop libraries, information and resource centers, readership promotion and bridge the digital divide, collaborate with Non-Governmental organizations (NGOs) and other stakeholders in the implementation of global and regional commitment for girls and women empowerment/initiatives through gender awareness, more efficient economy-wide policies. AWLIN Kaduna State Chapter has also been contributing to the achievement of economic growth and helping in identifying the social goals, of the communities or societies which it's empowering. More so, initiating the participation of women increases in decision-making at all levels.

Community development is the course of progress that works on the existence of individuals in the community. As per Huberman, Tom, and Laura, (2014) characterized community development as a cycle which includes subjectively and quantitatively changing individuals, their current circumstance, values and social cycles. This infers that for any significant developmental projects to take place, all kinds of people should take an interest. From the abovementioned, obviously community development requires the endeavors of residents both physical and material, (Kelly and Caputo, 2016). It is on this ground that women were perceived as one of the gatherings in the society whose endeavors are profoundly required for the development of community projects. Ewelum and Mbara, (2015) characterized community development as development advance a better living for the entire society. Functionally, community development can be characterized as the cycle by which a community come all in all likewise works helpfully toward finding goals to the difficulties that impact their local communities. It is vital to understanding the outline of community development since it helps in rural development, advancement of educational centres/schools/instructive focuses and their libraries, improvement of wellbeing in the community, agricultural growth and the improvement in the general expectations for everyday comforts of individuals at the local community level. Subsequently, a bunch of people residing commonly in an exact spot, for example, a region made up of a community. Significantly, UNDP. (2018) proposed that to personality any community development projects which could works on the existences of the community have attributes which are widespread, for example, getting affects by all individuals impacted by change, regard nearby information and utilize neighborhood ability, assemble neighborhood limit, that is long

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heave community maintainability relies upon creating human and social capacities and compelling, straightforward correspondence. Considering the above affirmation, it basic to express that there is, no community development projects that can be effectively achieved without the dynamic association and cooperation of women in such society. On this position, it becomes fundamental for the help of women cooperation in community development project through activation.

Rally is one of the fundamental procedures of community development project. Rally can be characterized as an endeavor to bring both human and non-human together to embrace formative exercises or project to accomplish reasonable advancement. In Ajayi and Otuya, (2016), assembly is the most common way of placing individuals into status for dynamic help or of stimulating the interest and cognizance of a gathering in a programme, which would be good for them. There is a presumption that, the expected members have not become mindful of the presence, the goals or the benefits to be gotten from the program. Kelly and Caputo, (2016) as he would like to think noticed that rally and refinement of the community empowers the supporters of the project to have the amazing chance to examine exchange and answer questions which on the off chance that not treated at beginning phase will later mischief the venture. United Nations Development Programmes (UNDP), (2016) noticed that rallying includes making consciousness of specific issues existing community and which need earnest consideration. Functionally, rally subsequently, is giving sufficient information concerning a programme items and items to get the help and cooperation of individuals in the programme. Huberman, Tom and Laura, (2014) noticed that most development revolved around individuals and to this end perhaps of the most tireless worry being developed writing is about ways individuals might rally for given programs or for the goal of given issues that encroach on development itself. In this way, obviously any community which neglects to foster the abilities and useful gifts of her kin and to successfully rally and use such abilities to change the community economy could not be able to accomplish genuine turn on of the developments. To that end, rally is significant for c compelling implementation of any community development projects.

However, other strategies for powerful implementation of proof based women librarian's cooperation in community development projects as placed by UNDP Women, (2018), incorporate the followings: to get solid authority, to lay out a conventional design, to draw in different associations, community pioneers, and occupants, to guarantee bona fide support and shared navigation, to guarantee legitimate and useful jobs for youngsters, to foster a common vision, to direct a necessities evaluation, to make a well thought out course of action, to carry out commonly building up systems, to think up a gathering pledges procedure, to lay out compelling channels for interior correspondence, to teach the community women, to direct process and result assessments, and to assess the community preparation exertion independently. Also, according to Huberman, Tom and Laura (2014) and UNDP, (2016) who reported that, Women librarians could play a vital role in improving access to information in their communities among women about the importance of women's participation in community development projects. Such as helping to create and manage community schools or public libraries, provide literacy training and facilitate access to digital resources, promote gender equality and advocate for women's rights, challenge gender discrimination and stereotypes, engaging women librarian's in decision-making processes as it can affect their community development project, building supportive networks for women can connect, share experiences and ideas, and provide mutual support for each other, assist to promote health education, provide access to health resources, and advocate for health policies that benefit women and their families, encourage collaboration among women, other community members and stakeholders which may assist them to build strong partnerships and promote collective action towards achieving common goals, assist in promoting community dialogue and facilitate community-based initiatives, lead to improvements in democratic governance and the protection of human rights, celebrating the successes of women, their achievements and contributions to community development, can also lead to a vital economic benefits to the development of their communities (IFLA, 2019).

Therefore, community development projects will be sustained by creating opportunities for women's continued participation in community development projects. Ewelum and Madu (2016) and Ugwu, (2010) likewise proposed strategies for development for women librarian's interest in community development projects, which include: assembling women for social change, security of finished projects, satisfactory use of accessible resources, giving the connection between the community and the government, non-governmental organizations or donors, goals of struggles and conflict as they emerge in the communities, empowering women interest, being developing exercises, guaranteeing that women air their perspectives, including women in checking and assessment of undertakings, testing improper way of behaving or outer factors, overseeing and raising of assets through various sources, keeping up with cheerful relationship with women, prioritization of community needs, giving sufficient information to the women assuming requirements emerge, taking on straightforward authority among the women, including women in settling community issues, coordinating authority preparing for pioneers, incorporating women in developing projects, development of imposing associations, and utilization of incorporated rustic turn of events (Ike, 2015).

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More so, an efficacious rally emphasizes public involvement to generate fresh concepts and resources inside the community. Therefore, this calls for the involvement of women librarian’s in the project's decision-making, planning and execution. Also by employing women librarian and others in community women or initiatives, activation encourages residents to take part in community development projects. Women librarian’s active involvement could assist any community development initiatives as they undertake success. Furthermore, this can promote self-assistance and makes best use of available human and material resources for community development projects for effective execution of community development projects by women librarians in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this research are:

- i. Identify the problems that hinder the effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects.
- ii. Assess the strategies for effective implementation of women librarians’ participation in community development projects.

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What are the problems that hinder the effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects?
- ii. What are the strategies for effective implementation of women librarians' participation in community development projects?

Methodology

The researcher adopted descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 260 women librarians in tertiary institutions libraries from Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The sample of the study was 260 women librarian's using purposive sampling technique. Research instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. Research instrument for data collections was subjected to content and face validated by experts, among which was Measure and Evaluation, Librarians and Community Leaders. Consistency of the instrument was ensured using Cronbach Alpha method which yielded reliability co-efficient of 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. A mean score of 2.42 was used to make decision. Also criterion mean of 2.34 was used for decision.

Results

Research Question One:

What are the problems that hinder the effective implementation of women's participation in community development projects?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviations on Problems that Hinder Effective Implementation of Women Librarian's Participation in Community Development Projects

S/N	Items Statement – Problems	M	SD	Decision
1.	Traditional imitations/norms/religion	2.89	0.44	Agreed
2.	Lack of education/Illiteracy/ignorance	2.85	0.44	Agreed
3.	Lack of rallying strategies/ management know-how/Intercultural competence	2.72	0.45	Agreed
4.	Lack of co-operation between stakeholders/community capacity	2.71	0.45	Agreed
5.	Embezzlement of public fund/non-priority nature of projects/poor accountability	2.60	0.45	Agreed
6.	Lack of interest and involvement in participation	2.82	0.45	Agreed
7.	Poor leadership skills/ selfish interest of some leaders	2.91	0.44	Agreed
8.	Politically excluded/not given right to vote	2.66	0.46	Agreed
9.	Inadequate publicity and communication networking before and during the project	2.58	0.46	Agreed
10.	Miserable poverty/poor financial status of women	2.68	0.45	Agreed
11.	Gender equality/good for child bearing/house keeping	2.76	0.45	Agreed

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	Conflicts/insecurity	2.70	0.45	Agreed
Cumulative		2.57	0.45	

The result of data collected in respect to research question on in Table 1 revealed that all the items from 1 - 12 were agreed to be the problems that hinder effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects. This is because all the items have mean responses above the criterion mean of 2.50, which indicates positive responses to the items, with a cumulative mean response of 2.57 and a standard deviation of 0.45 respectively. More so, respondents accepted that, all items in table 1 were problems and challenges that hinder effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects.

Research Question Two:

What are the Strategies for Effective Implementation of Women's Participate in Community Development Projects?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviations on strategies for effective implementation of women's participate in community development projects

S/N	Items Statement - strategies for effective implementation	M	SD	Decision
1.	Women enlightenment and education and sustainable developments	2.99	0.43	Agreed
2.	Encouraging women participation in development activities	2.89	0.44	Agreed
3.	Involving women in monitoring and evaluation of community projects	2.79	0.45	Agreed
4.	Providing access to adequate information needs among women on community development project	2.69	0.45	Agreed
5.	Improvements in democratic governance and the protection of human rights	2.58	0.46	Agreed
6.	Success celebration and barriers as they maintaining cordial relationship among women	2.73	0.45	Agreed
7.	Ensuring genuine participation of women librarians in decision-making	2.76	0.45	Agreed
8.	Organizing leadership training for leaders and transparent leadership among the women	2.71	0.45	Agreed
9.	Building supportive networks for women to connect, share experiences and ideas and provide mutual support for advocacy activities	2.88	0.44	Agreed
10.	Incorporate women librarians in community development projects,	2.67	0.45	Agreed
	Aggregate Mean	2.77	0.45	

The research question two presented in Table 2 revealed in items 1- 10 were accepted by the women librarians as the strategies for effective implementation of women participate in community development projects such as; women enlightenment and education and sustainable development, encouraging women librarian’s participation in development activities, involving women in monitoring and evaluation of community projects, providing access to adequate information needs among women, improvements in democratic governance and the protection of human rights, success celebration and barriers as they maintaining cordial relationship among women, ensuring genuine participation of women librarians in decision-making, organizing leadership training for leaders and transparent leadership among the women, building supportive networks for women to connect, share experiences and ideas and provide mutual support for advocacy activities, assimilate women librarians in community development projects.

Items in Table 2 were with a total mean score of 2.77 and 0.45 standard deviation respectively. Therefore, they respondents accepted that all the items on the table were indication of acceptance on the strategies for effective implementation of women librarians participate in community development projects in Zaria metropolis of Kaduna State Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Findings on research question one revealed in Table 1 as problems that hinder effective implementation of women's participation in community development projects. Result of data analyzed revealed that all the items in table were accepted by the respondents as challenges that hinder effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects. Problems range from Traditional imitations/norms/religion, Lack of education/Illiteracy/ignorance, Lack of rallying strategies/ management know-how/Intercultural competence, Lack of co-operation between

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stakeholders/community capacity, Embezzlement of public fund/non-priority nature of projects/poor accountability, Lack of interest and involvement in participation, Poor leadership skills/ selfish interest of some leaders, Politically excluded/not given right to vote, Inadequate publicity and communication networking before and during the project, Miserable poverty/poor financial status of women, Gender equality/good for child bearing/housekeeping and Conflicts/insecurity.

At a close look this finding of the study is in consonant with the findings revealed that the current finding shared direct relationship with the findings of Imhabekhai, (2019) which revealed that there was mainstream of women- are communally and politically excluded from participating in community development projects, planning arid decision-making processes. Findings of Enemu, (2011) also revealed women librarians who represent a considerable proportion of the total population in Nigeria as illiterate which also one of the factors that hinder effective implementation of women's participation in community development projects, finding in agreement with Ewelum, and Madu, (2016) revealed that lack of decision-making power affects women librarian politically in community development project participation. More so, it was revealed that a lot of community development projects were started and abandoned before competing them as a result of insufficient funds while available funds were not properly utilized due to corruption, embezzlement and lack of transparency among stakeholders and leader.

Findings on research question two revealed that, the results in Table 2 revealed strategies for effective implementation of women librarian's participation in community development projects. These strategies range from Women enlightenment and education and sustainable development, Encouraging women librarians, participation in development activities, Involving women in monitoring and evaluation of community projects, Providing access to adequate information needs among women, Improvements in democratic governance and the protection of human rights, Success celebration and barriers as they maintaining cordial relationship among women, Ensuring genuine participation of women librarians in decision-making, Organizing leadership training for leaders and transparent leadership among the women, Building supportive networks for women to connect, share experiences and ideas and provide mutual support for advocacy activities and Assimilate women librarian's in community development projects.

Finding is in line with a study conducted by IFLA. (2019) which revealed that strategies for improving women librarian's participation in community development projects, which include: rallying of women for social change, protection of completed projects, adequate utilization of available resources, resolutions of conflicts and disagreement as they grow in such communities, encouraging women participation in development activities, ensuring that women air their views, involving women in monitoring and evaluation of projects, maintaining cordial relationship with women, providing adequate information to the women if needs arise, involving women in resolving community issues, and assimilate women in development projects. Finding is also in agreement with that of Kelly and Caputo, (2016) that rallying and creating awareness in the community enables the sponsors of the project to have the opportunity to discuss dialogue and answer questions which if not answered at earlier times which may affect the project in later time. It also agrees with that of UNDP. (2018) that, rallying in the rural areas involves using such strategies as mass media like town criers, video, posters, and pamphlets to motivate women and win their acceptance for change and development as well as involving the participants in the formation, implementation and evaluation of the community projects. This finding is in agreement with the finding of UNDP. (2016) that the organizing launchings, encourage community organization and ensuring sound leadership are also strategies for enhancing community development projects as stated.

Conclusion

From the finding of this study, it can be seen that, community leadership remains the mechanism by which individual's efforts are enabled to follow the continual swapping of energies and fulfillment for the instant community development projects. Therefore, in the process of bringing about attractive social changes in Zaria communities, a number of challenges persevere thus retarding the pace at which development is achieved. Such challenges can be ameliorated through some potential strategies that have been suggested in this research. Emphasizes are imperativeness on rallying, as the most basic strategies of community development projects which the concepts of rallying and community development were discussed. Research revealed that rallying is an essential aspect of engaging women librarians in community development projects because it supports meaningfully to the attainment of community development projects.

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Recommendations

The aim of this study was to investigate the impacts of women librarian's participation in community development projects in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna state, Nigeria based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

1. Women librarians should strive to identify and address the barriers that prevent women librarians from participating in community development projects. Such as cultural and social norms, discrimination, and lack of access to education and resources. Strive for equal rights and opportunities to participate in community development projects in the decision-making process. Providing community development training for community-based women to equip them with the knowledge and skills of community development projects to help them participate in their communities can lead to economic empowerment. Women librarian leaders should adopt transparent leadership to avoid women's doubt in their leadership role. As they may call on government to encourage felt-needs projects by providing financial assistance to communities' projects that are most significant. Also advocate for women's rights, challenge gender discrimination and stereotypes. Such enables women acceptance of participatory approach to community development projects and be optimistic for efficient rally of women in community development projects.
2. Women librarians should promote community education, mostly for girls and women as community development projects. Such can be done by sponsoring the educational programmes and resources. Participation in education sectors can aid in social economic subsidy and decrease in poverty and conform-ability. Make an effort to organize rallies that should include other community women to ensure active participation in development projects. By so doing solid collaboration and common goals will be achieved. Build supportive networks for women to connect, share experiences and ideas, and provide mutual support which includes women's groups, and counselling. Seek for political rights of women so as to be given the right to vote and be voted for in some sensitive positions in the communities and protection, human rights, and democratic governance. And improving access to information in their communities among other women about the importance of women's participation in community development projects. Such can help establish and oversee the affairs of the community libraries, arrange for information literacy training, and ease access to digital resources.

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